

The AFRL Demonstration and Science Experiments (DSX) for DoD Space Capability in the MEO

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Abstract—The Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL) Space Vehicles Directorate has developed the Demonstration and Sciences Experiment (DSX) to research the technologies needed to deploy space assets in the harsh MEO radiation environment. The DSX comprises three basic research experiments: 1) Wave Particle Interaction Experiment, 2) Space Weather Experiment, and 3) Space Environmental Effects Experiment.

The Wave Particle Interaction Experiment will explore the transmission, propagation and amplification of very low frequency (VLF) waves in the magnetosphere. The experiment will be performed using a mission architecture that includes space transmitters and receivers on DSX, ground transmitters such as High frequency Active Auroral Research Program (HAARP), and other space receivers on satellites such as IMAGE (Imager for Magnetopause-to-Aurora Global Exploration). The specific objectives are to explore the effect of VLF waves on scattering energetic particles in the radiation belts, global wave propagation, amplification, and efficiency of VLF injection from a space antenna through the plasma sheath. The Wave Particle Interaction Experiment is under development through the strong support of DARPA's Sleight of HAND program

The Space Weather Experiment uses a combination of seven particle and field sensors to precisely measure high and low energy particle dose rates and pitch-angle distributions as well as local magnetic fields in the poorly characterized MEO environment and slot region.

The Space Environmental Effects experiment on DSX is centered around the NASA GSFC Space Environmental Testbed (SET) payload which will perform basic research on the performance of a number of electronics components in the MEO environment. In addition, AFRL radiometers and photometers will be used to characterize the radiation effects on select optical and thermal coatings.

Grouping these experiments on a single platform provides a low-cost opportunity for AFRL due to the experiments' common requirements and goals. All three experiments need a 3-axis stabilized spacecraft bus, a suite of radiation sensors, and extended duration in a MEO orbit.

The DSX spacecraft is currently in fabrication. The DSX program enjoys the continued support of SMC Det 12, Space Test Program, in the process to secure a launch manifest. The satellite is planned to be launch ready by late 2008 with one year of on-orbit operations.

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1. FLIGHT EXPERIMENT CONCEPT

The functional baseline configuration for the DSX flight experiment is shown in Figure 1. The core is the Evolved Expanded Launch Vehicle (EELV) Secondary Payload Adapter (ESPA) Ring [1,2], which is used to maximize launch opportunities on both Space Test Program (STP) and operational DoD launchers. ESPA was developed and designed by CSA Engineering. Every EELV launch is a potential ride for an ESPA ring, and thus for DSX. The ESPA ring serves as the primary structure for DSX, and is upgraded to provide host spacecraft functions (avionics, TT&C, ADCS, C&DH, and power management and distribution) by the addition of components packaged on an *avionics module* (AM). The DSX payloads (including deployable booms) are mounted on an identical structure, the *payload module* (PM), attached to the ESPA ring opposite the avionics module. The entire assembly is designed to be stowed within a 4-m diameter EELV fairing. The avionics and payload modules are under development at MicroSat Systems Inc. in Littleton, CO.

The design intent for the ESPA is to remain attached to the launch vehicle upper stage to facilitate deployment of up to six microsatellites. However, unlike the traditional ESPA

approach, the DSX avionics and payload modules do not separate; they remain attached. After the launch's primary satellite (DSX is secondary.) is deployed, the DSX ESPA separates from the EELV 2nd stage booster to become a free-flyer spacecraft. The ESPA ring serves as the DSX spacecraft's primary structure, with an upper separation interface to the primary payload adapter and a lower separation interface to the EELV upper stage adapter. Figure 2 shows DSX and identifies its major components in a stowed configuration. The experiment is baselined for flight in the radiation belts with a nominal orbit of 6,000 km x 12,000 km elliptical, mid-inclination, and 1-year of mission operations.

Figure 1 - DSX Flight Experiment Configuration (Deployed).

Figure 2 - DSX Baseline Design (Stowed, separation systems not shown)

From the earliest DSX conceptual planning, it was understood that the key to a successful program execution was maximizing DSX's compatibility with numerous launch vehicles. While the ESPA-based approach makes every EELV a potential ride, not all co-manifest opportunities possess sufficient excess launch vehicle performance needed to inject DSX into its uncommon MEO orbit. Therefore, flexibility in the design will be maintained for as long as practicable to allow repackaging DSX for flight on dedicated launchers. Inherent in the modular approach shown in Figure 2 is the ability to separate the two modules from the ESPA ring, and directly stack them in a vertical assembly for a dedicated launcher. The stacked configuration is shown in Figure 3, and views of DSX encapsulated in various launch fairings are shown Figure 4. This modular architecture not only makes DSX

reconfigurable for various launch vehicles, but it also greatly simplifies payload integration.

Figure 3 - DSX Stacked Configuration for Dedicated Launchers

Figure 4 - DSX stowed, encapsulated; left to right: Atlas V EELV (baseline ESPASat), Minotaur IV/V, and Falcon V

2. GROUND SEGMENT

The DSX ground segment consists of three major elements: mission control, global telemetry, tracking, and control (TT&C) network, and the remote experiment sites, as shown conceptually in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - DSX Ground Segment Overview

The mission will be operated out of both the Space and Missile Systems Center's Research, Development, Test and Evaluation Support Complex (Det-12/RSC) and AFRL's Missions Operations and Data Center (MOC/DC) facilities located at Kirtland AFB, NM. Det-12/RSC will provide the real-time contacts support, schedule the Air Force Satellite Control Network (AFSCN) TT&C, and acquire both spacecraft and payload data from the space vehicle. Commands will initially be developed from AFRL's MOC/DC facility where the effects will be simulated to validate proper operation. These commands will be sent to the RSC for uplink via Space-Ground Link System (SGLS) communication protocol to the DSX satellite. Down-linked information from the space vehicle state-of-health data will be validated from the real-time operations system located at the RSC. Data from remote experiment sites i.e., optical and radar ranges and VLF ground installations, are coordinated at the data center. All up-linked commands and down-linked telemetry and science data for DSX will be encrypted. In addition to SGLS communications bands, the DSX spectrum allocation application also includes VLF used for the Wave Particle Interaction Experiment. The RF emissions flow for DSX is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 - DSX RF Emissions Flow Diagram

All DSX data products, including real-time telemetry, stored state-of-health, stored and real-time experiment data, and ranging information, will be sent to the MOC/DC for further analysis and data archival. The DC will correct time tags, parse data files, collect data from remote sites (optical and radar ranges and VLF ground installations), and permanently archive the data. Experiment data and required spacecraft by-products will be distributed to each experiment team.

Preliminary orbit analysis performed for DSX has shown that AFSCN provides fairly continuous coverage over the orbit. Based on the need for AFSCN to prioritize operational assets, an average of 85 minutes of contact time per orbit, for a 5.3 hour orbit period (6,000 km x, 12,000 km) is assumed.

3. DSX EXPERIMENTS

Wave Particle Interaction Experiment

The Earth's radiation belts exhibit considerable dynamic behavior ranging from the creation and destruction of whole new belts in the outer zone (> 6000 km) occurring on time scales of minutes to days and the slower diffusion of the innermost regions (< 6000 km) occurring on timescales of months to years. A major cause of the energetic electron belt dynamics are wave-particle interactions driven by electromagnetic waves in the VLF range and below. Properly directed, this scattering will increase the electron velocity parallel to the local magnetic field by altering the "pitch-angle" (i.e. the angle between the particle's parallel and perpendicular velocity) and lower the altitude at which the electron magnetically reflects along the field line, an effect due to the conservation of magnetic moment (Figure 7). If the magnetic reflection is lowered to altitudes within the upper atmosphere, collisions with the plentiful neutral particles will lead to a depopulation of the radiation belt along that magnetic flux tube.

Figure 7 - Wave Particle Interaction Processes

Natural sources of VLF in the magnetosphere include magnetospheric hiss generated by space weather processes and lightning-induced whistler waves propagating along field-aligned ducts through the magnetosphere. To match current models of radiation belt dynamics to the observed behavior of electrons, it is necessary to postulate that man-made VLF leaking into the magnetosphere from ground-based submarine communications systems is also a significant source. Direct measurements of VLF power have been sparse because scientific satellites with the required capability (e.g. the USAF CRRES [3] and NASA IMAGE [4] missions) have been in highly elliptic orbits with apogee > 6 Earth radii and consequently spend most of their time outside the inner belt and slot region. Placing a VLF receiver on the DSX satellite will allow for a quantitative determination of the current levels of natural and man-made VLF waves in the inner magnetosphere. Models of ground-based VLF injection and global magnetospheric propagation will also be validated in a controlled manner. The VLF transmitter on DSX will provide the capability to conduct active experiments to quantify space-based VLF wave-injection efficiency and determine the details of the wave-particle interactions. An electron loss cone detector on DSX will allow direct

correlation of changes in energetic particle distributions with injected wave power. Accurate models of the VLF injection, propagation, and wave particle interaction processes will be developed and validated with DSX data. Such models are critical components of global radiation belt nowcast and forecast models required for space situational awareness and mission planning. The Wave Particle Interaction Experiment is under development through the strong support of DARPA's Sleight of HAND program. The payload consists of four major components, further described below.

The Wave-induced Precipitation of Electron Radiation (WIPER) Broadband Receiver (BBR) is a passive receiver designed to measure the natural and man-made ELF, VLF and LF signals in the inner magnetosphere in the 3-to-50-kHz range. The BBR is electrically connected to all four deployed booms shown in Figure 1, with two channels of the BBR measuring electric fields via the y and z-axis antennas, and three more channels measuring magnetic field about three axes of the Tri-axial Search Coil antennas (TASC). TASC is mounted on the tip of the +Z boom and the BBR is contained within the payload module. BBR measurements are also coordinated with high power transmissions of the WIPER transmitter, transmissions from ground based facilities, as well as naturally occurring sources of magnetospheric VLF (e.g., lightning). The WIPER BBR is being developed by Stanford University and Lockheed Martin.

The WIPER transmitter electronics consists of the Transmitter Controller Unit (TCU), integrated Narrowband Receiver (NBR), and two Transmitter Amplification and Tuner Units (TATU). Each TATU electrically connects to a pole of a center-fed dipole antenna supported by the $\pm Y$ booms shown in Figure 1. The transmitter electronics include dynamic tuning circuits. The VLF transmission system will draw on almost 1 kilowatt of energy while broadcasting in the 1-to-50-kHz range, and much smaller power levels from 50-to-750-kHz range. The transmission antenna elements that run along the Y-axis booms reach potentials of up to 10 kV. The TCU/NBR and both TATUs are housed within the payload module. The WIPER transmitter electronics are being developed by the University of Massachusetts at Lowell, benefiting from significant heritage resulting for a similar payload flown on NASA's IMAGE satellite.

The Loss Cone Imager (LCI) is an electron detector that will measure electron distribution in and around the "loss cone," the collection of electronics whose pitch angle with respect to the geomagnetic field vector are in the range that will result in reflection at or below an altitude of 100 km, the level at which atmospheric absorption can be assumed. The LCI consists of two scanning heads with $\pm 180^\circ$ motorized articulation. Each scanning head has a 180° by 6° field of view, so that together the full 4π spherical field of regard may be imaged. LCI depends on data from the

Vector Magnetometer (VMAG) for its motor pointing control loop and for data correlation.

A separate solid-state detector (SSD) telescope called the High Sensitivity Telescope (HST) will be mounted on DSX in order to obtain flux of energetic electrons along the geomagnetic field vector direction. This telescope is designed to have a geometric factor of $0.1 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ steradian}$ with sufficient shielding to permit the detection of $100 \text{ particles/cm}^2\text{-sec-steradian}$ in the loss cone. The LCI and HST is under development by Boston University and benefits from heritage of flight of similar instruments such as the Imaging Electron Spectrometer (IES) on the ESA-NASA Cluster satellites.

The Vector Magnetometer (VMAG) will be used to determine the direction of the magnetic field to better than one degree at all points in the orbit. This performance will allow the mapping of locally measured particle distributions to global distributions. VMAG sensors will measure the DC B-field over a 100-10000 nT range with $\pm 0.1 \text{ nT}$ accuracy at 20 Hz. VMAG data is also used in real time by the LCI, as previously discussed. VMAG will operate continuously to provide DC magnetic field and ULF wave environment data required by the Space Weather Experiment MEO space particle modeling experiment, thus it supports experiment objectives of both the Wave Particle Experiment and the Space Weather Experiment.

The VMAG electronics will be mounted within the payload module and the fluxgate sensor will be deployed on the tip of the $-Z$ boom, opposite TASC. VMAG is under development for DSX by UCLA, and is similar to other fluxgate magnetometers (shown in Figure 8) developed by UCLA that have flown on several missions.

Figure 8 - Fluxgate Sensor (left) and Electronics (right)

Space Weather Experiment

With an orbit of 6,000 km by 12,000 km, DSX will explore a large swath of the inner magnetosphere, in particular the outer region of the inner proton belt, the "slot region" between the belts, and inner regions of the outer electron belt. This domain has remained largely unexplored due to the understandable tendency of military, commercial, and scientific satellite systems to be located outside the intense regions of radiation: most satellites fly in LEO or GEO. However, increasing demands for uninterrupted coverage of the Earth are driving mission planners to consider putting satellite constellations in orbits spending significant time in

the inner magnetosphere. Current standard space particle models (e.g. AE-8 and AP-8) can be off by as much as 50 times or more in estimating the time taken to reach hazardous dose levels in the MEO regime. It is imperative that measurements be made of the plasma and energetic particles so that accurate forecast models can be developed to enable the successful design and operations of systems in these desirable orbit regimes. Accurate environment determination is important for DSX so that quantitative correlation with the performance of the spacecraft and its payloads over the course of the mission may be performed.

Deficiencies of current standard radiation belt models in the inner magnetosphere include the lack of (a) spectrally resolved, uncontaminated measurements of high-energy protons (10-400 MeV) and electrons (1-30 MeV) and (b) accurate low- to mid-energy (< 1000 keV) measurements of the energetic particle and plasma environment. Not surprisingly, most of the space weather data to date has been accumulated in the LEO and GEO regimes, as illustrated in Figure 9, with data from dosimeters aboard the TSX5 and DSP satellites in LEO and GEO, respectively. The Space Weather instruments onboard and unique orbit of DSX will address these deficiencies. Included will be electron and proton detectors to measure both the spectral content and angle of arrival of both species over broad energy ranges. An on-board magnetometer (VMAG, see above) will allow for the transformation of angle-of-arrival measurements into estimates of the flux distribution with respect to the local pitch-angle (i.e. the angle between the particle velocity and magnetic field). Local pitch-angle distributions can then be used to estimate global particle distributions by mapping techniques using the well-known equations of motion and magnetic field models tagged to the local measurements. The capabilities of Space Weather Experiment sensor suite are described in detail in the following sub-sections.

Figure 9 - Space Weather Data from TSX and DSP Shows Lack of Data in MEO

The Compact Environmental Anomaly Sensor (CEASE) is composed of two dosimeters, two particle telescopes and a Single Event Effect detector. CEASE has the capability to monitor a broad range of space hazards from surface damage and charging (keV electrons) to Single Event Effects resulting from >100 MeV cosmic rays and solar protons [5,6]. The angular field-of-view for CEASE is relatively large and will not resolve pitch-angle distribution. CEASE will be mounted on an exterior panel of the payload

module. One change for DSX is that CEASE will capture and downlink the full dose spectra from each dosimeter, whereas prior versions only captured six reduced data points (two for low LET data and four for high LET data). The CEASE instrument was developed by Amptek, Inc. and has already flown on several spacecraft. CEASE and the other instruments of the Space Weather Experiment are shown in Figure 10.

The Low Energy Electrostatic Analyzer (LEESA) will measure energy fluxes and energy spectra for low-energy electrons and protons (100 eV to 50 keV). These low-energy particles are responsible for surface electric charging and damage to thin films such as thin-film photovoltaics, conventional solar cell cover glasses, and coatings. LEESA will be mounted on an exterior panel of the avionics module. It is under development for DSX by Amptek.

The High Energy Imaging Particle Spectrometer (HIPS) will measure electrons with energies between 1-10 MeV and protons with energies between 30 and 300 MeV. These high-energy particles are responsible for microelectronics damage, displacement and total dose damage, SEEs, and deep dielectric charging. HIPS will be mounted on an exterior panel of the payload module. It is under development for DSX by Physical Sciences, Inc (PSI).

The Low Energy Imaging Particle Spectrometer (LIPS) is designed to measure the ring current particles that are important in the energy flow processes in the magnetosphere. This particle population plays an important role in spacecraft charging and surface damage due to sputtering. The instrument, built by Physical Sciences Inc, uses specially designed combinations of scintillator materials to detect electrons and protons with energies between 20 keV and 1 MeV. Eight 10-degree by 8-degree apertures will provide pitch angle resolution. LIPS will be mounted on an exterior panel of the payload module, and is also being developed by PSI.

Figure 10 - Space Weather Instruments (CEASE, LEESA, HIPS, and LIPS)

Space Environmental Effects

The Space Environment Testbed (SET) carrier, under development by NASA GSFC provides standard mechanical, electrical, and thermal interfaces for a collection of small flight investigations. The general areas of investigation of the instruments carried on SET fall in the following categories:

- (1) Characterization of the space environment.

- (2) Performance improvement for microelectronics used in space.
- (3) Accommodation and/or mitigation of space environment effects for detectors & sensors.
- (4) Accommodation and/or mitigation of charging/discharging effects on spacecraft and spacecraft components.
- (5) Definition of mechanisms for materials' degradation and performance characterization of materials designed for shielding from ionizing radiation.

The first SET mission, SET-1, will fly on DSX. SET-1 consists of the following specific investigations (also refer to Figure 11):

Cosmic Ray Environment Dosimetry and Charging (Credance) measures the radiation environment (total dose), and the charging environment during normal background and space weather events. Credance measurements include:

- (1) Proton flux > 40 MeV per unit solid angle.
- (2) Charge deposition in large silicon diodes arranged in telescopes (Pulse height analysis is used to obtain ion linear energy transfer (LET) spectra of heavy ions in the 100-to-25000-MeV cm²/g range.).
- (3) Threshold voltage shift as a function of time to measure total ionizing dose in silicon at 2 different shielding depths.
- (4) Charging current at 3 different shielding depths which provides energetic electron flux measurements at 3 energies.

Credance measurements overlap in part with the CEASE space weather instrument, and will provide for mutual validation and data correlation of both instruments. Credance has been developed by QinetiQ/UK.

Dosimetry Intercomparison and Miniaturization (DIME) will measure space radiation environments which are detrimental to space system reliability using novel dosimetry techniques. DIME occupies two 3U card slots on the SET-1 carrier, and is being developed by Clemson University. Specific DIME measurements include:

- (1) Radiation-Sensing Field-Effect Transistor (RADFET) threshold voltage shift as a function of time and converted to total ionizing dose.
- (2) Erasable Programmable Read-only Memory (EPROM) threshold voltage shift as a function of time and converted to total ionizing dose (also, the rate number of single event upsets as a function of radiation level).
- (3) Static Random Access Memory (SRAM) single event upsets at various potentials and conversion to dose

also, the rate number of single event upsets as a function of radiation level).

- (4) Linear Energy Transfer (LET) Spectrometer pulse height spectra as function of time and converted to LET to measure ions including protons.
- (5) Optically Stimulated Luminescent (OSL) Films visible emission spectrum as a function of time to measure micro-dose.

Focused on characterization of proton effects and Enhanced Low Dose Rate Sensitivity (ELDRS) in Bipolar Junction Transistors (BJT), ELDRS measures radiation-induced total ionizing dose and displacement damage on linear devices sensitive to enhanced space low-dose-rate effects. ELDRS will measure base and collector currents for 24 COTS BJTs as functions of the emitter and gate voltages and time. ELDRS is being developed by Arizona State University.

COTS-2 measures particle-induced single event effects on an SEE mitigation platform in normal backgrounds and during solar storm events. COTS-2 will measure a SEE on COTS FPGAs, classify the event by event type, and determine if mitigation of the effect occurred without watchdog intervention. COTS-2 is being co-developed by NASA and CNES.

Figure 11 - SET-1 (red plate is none-flight)

DSX will fly several photometers and radiometers (see Figure 12), developed by AFRL's Propulsion Directorate (Edwards, AFB). Together these will directly measure changes in optical transmission, thermal absorption and emission due to the MEO radiation environment. Coupon-level testing of specific developmental coatings intended for thin-film photovoltaics may also be performed using these sensors.

Figure 12 - Radiometers (left) and Photometers (right)

Mechanical Packaging

The design for both the avionics and payload modules, and mechanical arrangement and packaging of payloads within the payload module has been performed by MicroSat Systems, Inc (MSI). The resulting payload module equipment layout is shown below (Figure 13).

Figure 13 - Mechanical Packaging and Layout of Payloads

4. CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS

The DSX mission starts with launch as a secondary payload on an EELV. During launch, DSX is in a minimally powered state, so that it may detect a separation signal. Following separation of the primary payload from atop DSX, the EELV upper-stage will re-start in order to inject DSX into its intended orbit. At this point, DSX separates from the upper stage. Upon detection of the separation signal, DSX will autonomously undergo a series of scripted commands to initialize the bus. After acquisition of signal from the ground, and verification of nominal operation, the bus solar arrays deploy from the avionics module, and the attitude control system will activate in a sun-safe mode in order to orient the spacecraft into a power-positive attitude. Ground controllers will then perform various checks to verify the spacecraft state of health before initiating any boom deployments. Booms will be deployed in pairs (y-axis pair and z-axis pair) to minimize inertial imbalances. During boom deployments the attitude control system is placed in a less responsive mode in consideration of the fact that the center of pressure and moments of inertia of the spacecraft will vary significantly. Upon completion of these deployments, additional in-orbit tests are performed before the spacecraft assumes an operational mode. The scheduling of the sequence of events from separation through entering the operational phase is being developed, and the sequence's duration is expected to be less than one week.

Once the spacecraft is operational, routine commanding and data collection will be initiated as discussed in Section 2.1 (Ground Segment). Because spacecraft resources (namely power and data volume) are limited, and because certain experiments can only be operated at certain times,

experimental payloads are prescribed duty cycles to fit within the capabilities of the spacecraft. In general, instruments of the Space Weather Experiment will operate continuously with only limited ground intervention, such as occasional commanding to adjust threshold and gain settings. The instruments would only be turned off under low power conditions. The SET-1 payload will have two modes of operation, a low-power mode where only Credance is powered and collecting data, and the normal mode where all SET experiment investigations are operating. While in normal mode, measurements take place on a set interval, with some measurements triggered by the on-board orbit propagator, which will indicate to SET-1 the timing of ascending and descending node crossings. The most demanding requirements are associated with the Wave Particle Interaction Experiment, since its associated payloads consume the greatest power (during the high power Whistler transmission mode) and also generate the most data, as collected from the Broadband Receiver. For science reasons, the high power transmissions can be constrained to occur when the spacecraft is within $\pm 20^\circ$ latitude of equatorial, and because of power limitations, the transmission durations will generally be limited to no more than 30 minutes per orbit. Figure 14 is a plot of payload power demand over a period of five days. The plot was prepared by Planning Systems, Inc. A more detailed year-long mission timeline is being prepared to plan all DSX operations and coordinate ground resources.

Figure 14 - Payload Power Profile: a Week in the Life of DSX

5. SPACECRAFT DRIVING REQUIREMENTS

The science objectives of DSX impose certain mission-specific driving requirements on the design of the spacecraft bus and payloads. These are identified here. The nominal MEO orbit (6000 x 12000 km, mid-inclination), results in a fairly severe radiation environment because of prolonged residence in the upper Van Allen belts. The total ionizing dose (TID) for the mission is approximately equivalent to 10 krad/year behind 8 mm of Aluminum shielding. The results of radiation dose analyses performed for DSX are shown in Figure 15. The implication of this is that all DSX

equipment must be designed to survive the radiation environment, through the use of shielding, selection of radiation and SEU-tolerant or hardened components, or a combination of these approaches.

Figure 15 - Total Ionizing Dose for DSX Mission

With respect to flight orientation, the attitude control system must provide 3-axis stabilization, maintain a power positive attitude throughout the mission, and orient the spacecraft such that the VLF antennas are aligned normal to the local magnetic field line when spacecraft is within $\pm 20^\circ$ of equatorial (i.e., when VLF propagation experiments and measurements will be performed). Pointing requirements are fairly relaxed with a 2° control and a 1° knowledge requirements deemed to be sufficient.

6. RESPONSIVE ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES

Historically, spacecraft payloads have been produced via end-to-end development of the entire payload system as well as significant development of key satellite bus components with interfaces to the payloads such as the flight computer and power management system. As part of this effort, a considerable fraction of the engineering development required to produce a working system is devoted to specifying, developing, and testing the components designed to perform payload functions that, in general, fall under the category of payload interface electronics for data acquisition and control. This approach is not conducive to rapid-response missions because it depends on monolithic integration methods. Monolithic integration of a satellite involves assembly of many components simultaneously. This can present an integration and test nightmare, where debugging problems found in system level testing and routine maintenance of the vehicle can be very complex and costly to perform.

Modular integration, on the other hand, allows major subsystems and payload modules to be fully integrated and

functionally tested separately. System level testing can be performed in a “FlatSat” configuration, pre-integration where the subsystems are wired together using test harnesses to verify connectivity and test closed-loop performance. This allows for much faster isolation of problems and shorter integration spans.

DSX maximizes the benefits of modular integration via an architecture that requires that all devices adhere to a standard interface for control and communications (electrical, power, command & communications protocol). This is enabled by the use of dual-redundant network interface cards in the Experiment Computer System (ECS) chassis that provide for command and data interface between the flight control computer and all payloads. Rather than a single on-board computer responsible for handling all spacecraft functions, DSX unburdens the main spacecraft computer from payload-related operations by providing a dedicated payload-interface computer: the ECS, under development by Planning Systems, Inc. This architecture decouples the requirements of the flight computer with the design of the payloads, allowing for a completely standardized spacecraft flight computer, almost independent of payload requirements. The highly capable ECS design is also generalized in nature, so that it can handle a wide range of payload types and classes simultaneously, with low data latency. An ECS block diagram is provided in Figure 16., below.

Figure 16 - Experiment Computer System (ECS)

These modular avionics technologies complement the modular reconfigurable mechanical design, and together represent a path finder for future rapid-response spacecraft. With this approach, the DSX avionics module can be designed, integrated, and delivered before all the payloads have completed their development cycle, or even been selected. The next evolutionary step for this technology involves adding networking capabilities and enhancing the flight control computer so preprogrammed self-configuration of spacecraft subsystems, components, devices, and payloads is possible.

7. SUMMARY

AFRL's DSX mission is well underway. The Spacecraft Systems Requirements (SRR) was completed in the fall of 2004. Avionics, spacecraft bus, and Experiment Computer System Preliminary Design Reviews (PDR's) were completed in 2005, and most payloads will have reached the PDR milestone by the first quarter of 2006. With the fully integrated avionics module, depopulated payload module, and ESPA ring scheduled for delivery to AFRL in the first quarter of 2007, and all flight payloads delivered for AI&T by April 2008, DSX is currently on track to be launch-ready by late FY08. The DSX mission will provide an important database from which future designers of space missions intended to operate in the MEO environment can rely.

- New climatology models for satellite design in MEO will be developed as a result of DSX
- Key wave-particle interaction components of global radiation belt space situational awareness and forecast models will be developed and validated from the DSX data
- New methods for ruggedization of electronics for MEO will be tested

Beyond the inherent value of the scientific experiments, DSX is also path-finding a new, responsive approach for integrating spacecraft. The ESPA platform ensures affordable and frequent opportunities for launch. In addition, the combination of a dedicated payload/experiment computer and modular integration approach, allows a "standard" host spacecraft bus to be used, limiting the development risk to the experiments alone.

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Specific content provided by others includes many of the images in this paper. Specifically, all stowed and deployed views of the spacecraft (Figures 1, 2, 4, and 13) were provided by MSI, Figures 3, 14, and 16 were provided by Planning Systems. Images of VMAG components (Figure 8) were provided by UCLA. In Figure 10, images of CEASE and LEESA were provided by Amptek, and those of HIPS and LIPS were provided by Physical Sciences. The SET-1 image (Figure 11) was provided by NASA GSFC.

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The following references are not directly called out in this paper, but nonetheless provide background material on related subjects: